

Sustainability plan through social action

2025

Stefania Oikonomou, Katerina Zourou

Deliverable Factsheet

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Author(s):	Stefania Oikonomou, Katerina Zourou
Graphic Designer	Claire Fragiadaki
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Partnership

Partner n°	Name	Short name	Country	Logo
1.	University Paris 8	UP8	France	
2.	University Bordeaux Montaigne	UBM	France	
3.	Web2Learn	W2L	Greece	
4.	University of Ljubljana	UL	Slovenia	
5.	Polish Rectors Foundation	PRF	Poland	
6.	Lviv Polytechnic National University	LPNU	Ukraine	
7.	University of Hamburg	UH	Germany	
8.	Kaunas University of Technology	KTU	Lithuania	

Project summary

This publication is a result of the Eu-funded AGILE project (“Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition”, <http://www.agileproject-erasmus.eu/>), whose aim is to increase the resilience of HE systems to address the ongoing needs of refugees through social participation and skills recognition.

The AGILE project aims to enrich HE curricula by proposing new pedagogical designs that encourage grassroots and digitally enhanced actions in both formal and informal learning environments.

The project is coordinated by the University Paris 8. The consortium is made up of six universities (University Paris 8, Bordeaux Montaigne, University, University of Hamburg, University of Ljubljana, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Kaunas University of Technology), one think-tank (Polish Rectors Foundation) and one business partner (Web2Learn) specialised in open recognition systems and social learning.

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List of abbreviations

The following list presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviation	Meaning
EU	European Union
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institution
WP	Work Package

Introduction

Following the implementation of the WP3 interventions, the summer school and the WP4 academia-society experimentations, the AGILE project aims to assess a) their impact at individual and institutional levels, and b) their economic and social sustainability.

Specifically, the sustainability plan measures impact of the following AGILE activities:

- WP3A3 Level #1 intervention: instructional design.
- WP3A4 Level #2 intervention: social participation in and outside university.
- WP3A5 Level #3 intervention: open recognition of skills.
- WP3A9 AGILE Summer school.
- WP4A2 Academia-society experimentation #1: industry-academia to tackle refugee crises “Innovation 5.0”.
- WP4A3 Academia-society experimentation #2: crowd initiatives inside and outside the university “Living labs 2.0”.
- WP4A4 Academia-society experimentation #3: academic libraries as niches of social cohesion.
- WP4A5 Academia-society experimentation #4: managing massive number of unexpected refugees at HEIs: implementation in emergency situations.
- WP4A6 Academia-society experimentation #5: staff response to a crisis.

Why measure sustainability?

AGILE partners have presented key insights and results of their activities in a series of publications (e.g., Zourou, Oikonomou, 2023; Melo-Pfeifer, Gerwers, 2023; Jonaitytė, Štuopytė, Tautkevičienė, 2024; Boichenko, Oikonomou, Zourou, 2025) that are publicly available on the project’s website (<https://agileproject-erasmus.eu/>).

However, the partnership acknowledged the need to evaluate the impact of the AGILE social actions to the HE staff and students involved in them, so as to identify key sustainability measures that need to be adopted to ensure integration and long-term viability of the AGILE social actions within academic communities and activities.

Finally, this plan includes insights provided to the sustainability surveys distributed to HE staff and students (participants of the AGILE social actions) aiming to share their experience with other European HEIs that wish to adopt social action for crisis response.

Methodology

The authors of this plan developed an impact assessment methodology which is carried out at 2 levels, namely at individual and partner institutions' levels. Hence, 2 distinctive surveys (see ANNEX I and II) have been created:

- 1.a survey targeting HE staff of AGILE partners who organised and participated in WP3 and WP4 actions.
- 2.a survey targeting HE students who participated in WP3 and WP4 actions.

The minimum of replies to each survey was 2 per partner institution and the collection period was from January to March 2025. All data collected through the survey are compliant with the EU GDPR Regulation.

The surveys included both quantitative- and qualitative-oriented questions to allow an enriching and meaningful assessment of the impact of the actions, as well as give respondents the opportunity to share more insights and recommendations in terms of sustainability.

Overall, the HE staff survey was filled in by 16 individuals (2 per partner institution), and the HE students one by 19 individuals, thus highlighting a diverse and important pool of replies that will be presented below.

Impact and sustainability of AGILE social actions: HE staff

The WP5A5 survey was filled in by 16 higher education (HE) staff (2 per partner institution), as demonstrated in Figure 1 below.

3. AGILE partner institution 16 responses

Figure 1. HE staff respondents per AGILE partner

Respondents were called to provide their views on the impact of the AGILE social actions on their institution, as well as share insights on economic and social sustainability of social actions. As HE staff participated in a plethora of AGILE social actions, the survey organisers asked them to select 2 actions in which they took part to gather more insights on the impact of the AGILE social actions.

Section: Impact of the AGILE actions at institutional level

Through an open-ended question, the survey encouraged respondents to share their thoughts on the impact of 2 AGILE social actions in their institution.

Impact of 1st AGILE social action

Half of the replies came from HE staff who participated in the AGILE summer school and the WP4A2 Academia-society experimentation (50%), while the third most cited action was the WP3A3 Level #1 intervention.

By analysing respondents' replies to the question, it is observed how the AGILE actions were impactful at institutional level in 4 main sectors:

- **Expanding networking and collaboration among HEIs at national and European levels:** HE staff reported that their participation in the actions fortified their universities' connection and bonding with universities within and beyond their country, thus maximising HEIs' internationalisation potential.
- **Fostering pedagogical innovation in learning and research:** Respondents also highlighted the value and benefits generated from the AGILE social actions to innovation in learning and research of their institutions with regards to refugee inclusion and resilience. The design, outputs and reflections of the actions fostered new insights on how to approach and apply social action for crisis response from a pedagogical perspective.
- **Building HEIs' capacity in managing refugee crises:** From HE staff upskilling to strengthening of the social responsibility of HEIs, the implemented actions have built stronger and more action-oriented university communities in the face of crises.
- **Strengthening academia-society collaboration:** The majority of HE staff stated the impact of the actions in expanding and building strong collaborations among academia and societal actors (cf. civil society, business, etc.). Hence, by uniting forces with such actors for social good, HEIs become more aware and active in pursuing collaborations with stakeholders beyond academia.

Areas in which significant impact at institutional level is observed

Following the overview of impact assessment as shared by HE staff, respondents were asked to rate the degree of impact reached in a series of 10 fields, from academic excellence to social responsibility. The analysis of their replies showcases 4 areas in which the AGILE actions brought the most significant impact, namely:

- a) changes in staff attitudes,
- b) staff upskilling,
- c) synergies with civil society, and
- d) resilience in refugee crises.

Interestingly, these replies reflect the sectors of impact defined above, as they are directly linked to HEIs' capacity building and academia-society collaboration.

Do you believe that your institution is more impactful in terms of refugee crisis responsiveness as a result of this specific AGILE action?

In front of this question, all respondents marked the positive impact of the AGILE action in strengthening their institution's crisis responsiveness. The analysis of HE staff' replies emphasize how their HEIs have:

- Become more knowledgeable and action-oriented in the face of crises;
- Established connections with civil society and refugee communities, thus expanding the social mission and responsibility of academia;
- Enriched their teaching and learning practices and courses with innovative pedagogical approaches and tools.

Impact of 2nd AGILE social action

The majority of the replies came from HE staff who participated in the AGILE summer school (43.8%) and the WP4A2 Academia-society experimentation (18.8%).

The analysis of their replies to the impact of this second action to their institution reflects the 4 fields of impact identified by HE staff at the 1st AGILE social action as well. However, in this 2nd action, there is a divergence on the areas to which the actions brought more impact. Specifically, this time, HE staff shared that:

- a) staff upskilling,
- b) social responsibility,
- c) stakeholder engagement, and
- d) changes in staff attitudes

were the areas that have experienced more impact. A closer look at this change in the ranking of areas of impact can be interpreted as the willingness of HE staff to also highlight the importance of other aspects of the AGILE social actions, such as HEIs' social responsibility and stakeholder engagement which were not among the first 4 areas referred to at the 1st AGILE social action.

Do you believe that your institution is more impactful in terms of refugee crisis responsiveness as a result of this specific AGILE action?

Similarly to the replies provided for action 1, HE staff feel confident that the AGILE social action fortified their institution's ability to handle refugee crises. Moreover, it was also emphasized how the action enhance academia's visibility and credibility as a social actor ready to support refugees and contribute to collective efforts in times of crises.

Section: Economic sustainability

Ensuring financial support to academia-driven social actions is key for their sustainability in the long-term. Thus, the survey encouraged HE staff to share whether the resources they had at their disposal were sufficient to successfully execute the social actions. In particular, all respondents stated that resources received were sufficient to allow them to carry out quality activities and results.

What would make the academia-driven actions for refugees economically sustainable in your opinion?

Aiming to gather any useful insights on what could be improved to enhance financial viability of academia-driven social actions, all HE staff pointed to the need for more long-term funding and availability of resources. Hence, social actions need to be part of HEIs' regular planning and funding schemes to allow HE staff and students to develop and expand the impact of their actions within and beyond academia.

Most important economic resources to carry out academia-driven social actions

As reported by HE staff, the 2 most important resources are: a) funding and b) staff scarcity and availability; 2 very interrelated things that are deemed extremely important to organise and run successful social actions.

Section: Social sustainability

Sustainability of the AGILE social actions is also evaluated in terms of social responsiveness of the involved HEIs. Hence, to the question "Do you believe that your institution has become more open to embrace social actions as part of its educational activities?", HE staff, unanimously, stated that the AGILE social actions made their institution more socially responsible.

The foundation of this argument -as presented by HE staff replies- lies in the connections established between academia and social actors, as well as the upskilling of staff and students in society-oriented and innovative ways to think and act in the face of crises.

What would make the academia-driven actions for refugees sustainable in terms of social impact in your opinion?

To understand HE staff's attitudes and beliefs on the social value and sustainability of the AGILE social actions, this open-ended question encouraged them to share ideas and suggestions on the topics. The analysis of their replies brought to the fore the following areas of intervention:

- Ongoing dissemination of actions' outcomes and awareness raising on the value of social action.
- Keep engaging with social actors and communities.
- Integrating social actions within HE curricula and courses.
- Involving HE students as main advocates and organisers of social action for refugee resilience.

Most important social skills to carry out academia-driven social actions

Although social action is something that is taught and learned through practice, the AGILE partnership aimed to understand HE staff' perceptions over social skills which are deemed fundamental to participate in a social action. Their replies show that the 3 top social skills to carry out academia-driven social actions are:

- a) communication,
- b) respect, and
- c) teamwork.

All 3 reflect the importance of being inclusive, welcoming and open to listen, understand, co-design and act together with others to tackle a demanding social challenge, such as refugee crises.

Impact and sustainability of AGILE social actions: university students

The AGILE social actions included the active engagement and participation of HE students whose insights and feedback on the actions are deemed important to enrich our understanding of impact and sustainability of the AGILE social actions' approach. Thus, authors present replies of university students in their dedicated survey below.

Demographics

Out of the 19 respondents, 15 are identified as female and 4 as male. 6 of them reside in France, 4 in Poland, 3 in Germany and 3 in Ukraine, 2 in Slovenia and 1 in Lithuania. The majority of respondents were university students of AGILE partner organisations.

Section: Impact of the AGILE actions at individual level

Of the 19 respondents, 15 reported they participated at the AGILE summer school, while the rest were distributed among AGILE actions such as the workshops organised by UP8 and UBM, or the academia-society experimentations of W2L and KTU.

How much did your participation at the AGILE action increase your knowledge on refugee resilience and social actions?

As the AGILE social actions were something new for most participants, the survey called them to indicate which areas of their knowledge on refugee resilience and social action were particularly developed. Thus, the top 2 fields in which they stated they expanded their knowledge are:

1. academia's social responsibility and
2. societal resilience.

By looking at the objective and design of the AGILE social actions, it becomes evident the interrelation between them and the areas reported by respondents, as the primary goal of the actions was to strengthen public perceptions and attitudes towards academia' social mission as well as the value of contributing to societal resilience.

Section: Economic sustainability

Although the majority of respondents do not come from the administrative apparatus of universities, authors aimed to map participants' -particularly students'- views on what would make the academia-driven actions for refugees economically sustainable. By analysing their replies, the following dimensions emerge:

- Ensuring free or affordable education to refugees through the provision of tuition-free courses and scholarships.
- Supporting refugees' entrepreneurship through partnerships with business.
- Integrating long-term funding strategies for social action in universities' year planning.
- Advocating for grant Diversification, namely relying on multiple funding sources, such as government grants, philanthropic contributions, and international organizations.

Do you believe that participation in academia-driven social actions should be voluntary or remunerative?

Here, respondents' replies were diverse between those who reported that participation should be entirely voluntary and those who suggested a hybrid model including both. Specifically, argumentation over the importance of providing a hybrid model of voluntary and remunerative participation is based on 2 pillars:

- ensuring equal participation to the social actions for all, including individuals who lack the resources (tangible and intangible (time) to do so);
- keeping motivation of participants high throughout the action.

What comes out of the analysis of respondents' replies is that their position over remunerative participation is driven by the willingness to enhance engagement of every person in social action; as a way to strengthen inclusion and equality.

How important do you think follow-up funding to turn participants' ideas into action is?

The majority of respondents believe it's very important to ensure follow-up funding to apply participants' ideas into concrete projects.

3. On a scale from 1 (=not at all) to 5 (=extremely), how important do you think follow-up funding to turn participants' ideas into action is?

19 responses

Figure 2. Follow-up funding for projects' development

Section: Social sustainability

The AGILE actions aimed to bring a strong impact on participants' attitudes and beliefs towards social agency and action taking. Thus, in the question "How likely is it that you will take part in academia-driven social actions in the future?", the majority of respondents (90%) stated that it's extremely likely they will join academia-driven social actions (fig. 3).

1. On a scale from 1 (=not at all) to 5 (=extremely), how likely is it that you will take part in academia-driven social actions in the future?

19 responses

Figure 3. Participation in academia-driven social actions in the future

Do you feel more open to engage in actions that include multistakeholder collaboration for refugees' inclusion?

All respondents shared their eagerness to participate in social actions, especially those that include collaboration of multiple stakeholders, as they value the exchange of knowledge, ideas and experiences that come out of such process. The analysis of participants' openness to engage in social actions is facilitated by looking at statements like:

“From my perspective as a refugee, multistakeholder collaboration for inclusion is crucial because it brings together diverse support systems. Governments, businesses, NGOs, and academic institutions all have different resources and expertise that can make our integration smoother.”

“I believe that experience-sharing and collaboration between multiple stakeholders can create incredible opportunities for everyone involved. When universities, governments, NGOs, businesses, and local communities work together, they bring different perspectives, resources, and expertise to the table. This allows them to address the challenges of refugee inclusion more effectively than any single group could on its own”.

How much did your participation in the AGILE action increase your social skills for refugees' inclusion?

With regards to social skills development, the analysis of respondents' replies showcases that, for the majority of them, the AGILE social actions increased skills such as:

1. community bonding;
2. communication;
3. emotional intelligence and empathy.

These top 3 social skills developed by participants reflect also the socially-empowering potential of academia-driven social actions that move beyond traditional boundaries of education to reach communities in need.

Recommendations on sustainability

Beyond impact assessment, the WP5A5 surveys aimed to gather recommendations for sustainability of academia-driven social actions, as provided by both HE staff and students. Thus, we provide below an overview of recommendations showcased per field of intervention.

1.Ongoing funding: Although social actions usually rely on volunteerism and inherent willingness of participants, ensuring a stable funding mechanism that supports students' social actions is key to transform ideas into action.

2.Strong multistakeholder synergies and collaborations: As emphasised by a significant number of respondents, to achieve increased impact of social actions, as well as enhanced knowledge and skills of involved individuals, collaboration of multiple stakeholders is essential. From academia to business, civil society and policymaking, each social actor has valuable resources, expertise and potential to bring that can make academia-driven social actions truly powerful.

3.HE staff availability and upskilling: A crucial factor that affects sustainability of such actions is human resources, namely the availability of HE staff ready to support and/or guide students in setting up and implementing their social action. Coupled with staff availability, it's equally important to ensure HE staff upskilling in innovative pedagogies and methodologies, thus fostering new ideas and approaches to be applied in the actions.

4.Duration and integration in HE courses: Moving beyond the one-off events approach, the AGILE experience of social actions is a testimonial of the need to keep embracing social action as an ongoing activity to be sustained. To achieve this, it becomes indispensable to integrate social actions as part of HE courses and curricula to enhance recognition of students' and staff' work.

5.Community engagement and solidarity: Apart from HE staff' and students' upskilling and empowerment, social actions target communities' wellbeing, thus making community engagement a true added value of this approach. Hence, to fortify community engagement, HE staff should instill the sense of solidarity and empathy among students through adopting social action in teaching and learning practices and courses' design.

6.Co-design to ensure common vision and strategy: No social action can be successful and impactful if its objectives and implementation are not guided by a shared vision and strategy embraced by all individuals, communities and stakeholders involved. Thus, co-design of academia-driven social actions is a powerful way to ensure both ownership of the action by participants, as well as successful completion of it.

Testimonials of AGILE social actions

As part of the WP5A5 surveys, respondents were given the opportunity to share a brief testimonial by replying to the question: “What did your participation in the AGILE action teach you about yourself and social responsibility of academia in refugee crises?”. Prior consent of respondents was provided to gather and share their experiences. Thus, we present some of their testimonials here below.

“I realized that there are many active people around me with similar experiences, and the program showed how we can combine efforts and support one another. I still keep in touch with some participants, and together we continue working to help others.” - Maria Hrytsenko, student at the Silesian University of Technology, Poland.

“By participating in AGILE, I learned about my potential for empathy, adaptability and the power of collaborative problem-solving in addressing refugee issues. It deepened my understanding of the social responsibility of academia, highlighting how universities can serve as catalysts for change by providing education, research and resources to support refugee integration.” - Karina Osiiianenko, student at Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine.

“My participation in the AGILE action has deepened my understanding of the importance of social responsibility within academia, especially in the context of refugee crises. It taught me that education and academic initiatives are powerful tools for social change, enabling refugees to rebuild their lives and integrate into new societies.” - Habatullah Azizi, student at the University Bordeaux-Montaigne, France.

“Participating in the AGILE action taught me that academia has a vital role in refugee crises by not only providing education but also fostering long-term inclusion through research, policy advocacy, and skills development. It also reinforced my belief in the power of collaboration and the need for sustainable, impact-driven solutions.” - Ksenia Butenko, student at Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania.

“Participating in the AGILE action helped me realize that I am not alone in my experience of being abroad as a refugee. Despite our small differences in appearance and national identity, we are all just human—internally equal, ready to empathize with one another, support those around us, communicate, share our experiences, and offer advice.” - Vladislava Kachan, student at the University of Hamburg, Germany.

“There is no only one solution for everyone!” - Kaki Kalandarishvili, student at the University of Bordeaux-Montaigne, France.

“Thanks to the AGILE action I learned how to be social and work in groups.” - Hakmatullah Azizi, student at the University of Bordeaux-Montaigne, France.

“It has taught me about importance of social connections and how to build them in order to collaborate in socially driven actions. I discovered a lot more of how much the topic of refugees are personal and important for me.” - Sofiia-Liubov Mandryk, Ukrainian student at SGH Warsaw School of Economics, Poland.

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ANNEX I: Sustainability survey for HE staff

The survey distributed to staff of AGILE partner institutions is presented below.

Survey title: Impact of the AGILE actions at institutional level

Section: Action 1

1. From the actions you carried out, choose one to describe its impact at institutional level. Write its title and what kind of impact it has brought to your institution.

- WP3A3 Level #1 intervention: instructional design.
- WP3A4 Level #2 intervention: social participation in and outside university.
- WP3A5 Level #3 intervention: open recognition of skills.
- WP3A9 AGILE Summer school.
- WP4A2 Academia-society experimentation #1: industry-academia to tackle refugee crises “Innovation 5.0”.
- WP4A3 Academia-society experimentation #2: crowd initiatives inside and outside the university “Living labs 2.0”.
- WP4A4 Academia-society experimentation #3: academic libraries as niches of social cohesion.
- WP4A5 Academia-society experimentation #4: managing massive number of unexpected refugees at HEIs: implementation in emergency situations.
- WP4A6 Academia-society experimentation #5: staff response to a crisis.

2. Please rate the following areas of impact based on the outcomes of your AGILE actions at institutional level (scale 1-5, 1= not at all, 5=extremely)

Items:

1. Staff upskilling
2. Changes in staff attitude
3. Funding opportunities
4. Stakeholder engagement
5. Cooperation with the private sector
6. Synergies with civil society
7. Social responsibility
8. Academic excellence
9. Resilience in refugee crises (adaptability, innovation, problem-solving, etc.)
10. Integration of social action within courses

3. Do you believe that your institution is more impactful in terms of refugee crisis responsiveness as a result of this specific AGILE action? Please justify.

Section: Action 2

1. From the actions you carried out, choose one to describe its impact at institutional level. Write its title and what kind of impact it has brought to your university.

- WP3A3 Level #1 intervention: instructional design.
- WP3A4 Level #2 intervention: social participation in and outside university.
- WP3A5 Level #3 intervention: open recognition of skills.
- WP3A9 AGILE Summer school.
- WP4A2 Academia-society experimentation #1: industry-academia to tackle refugee crises “Innovation 5.0”.
- WP4A3 Academia-society experimentation #2: crowd initiatives inside and outside the university “Living labs 2.0”.
- WP4A4 Academia-society experimentation #3: academic libraries as niches of social cohesion.
- WP4A5 Academia-society experimentation #4: managing massive number of unexpected refugees at HEIs: implementation in emergency situations.
- WP4A6 Academia-society experimentation #5: staff response to a crisis.

2. Please rate the following areas of impact based on the outcomes of your AGILE actions at institutional level (scale 1-5, 1= not at all, 5=extremely)

Items:

1. Staff upskilling
2. Changes in staff attitude
3. Funding opportunities
4. Stakeholder engagement
5. Cooperation with the private sector
6. Synergies with civil society
7. Social responsibility
8. Academic excellence
9. Resilience in refugee crises (adaptability, innovation, problem-solving, etc.)
10. Integration of social action within courses

3. Do you believe that your institution is more impactful in terms of refugee crisis responsiveness as a result of this specific AGILE action? Please justify.

Section: Economic sustainability

1. The resources you had at your disposal for the organisation of this AGILE action were sufficient? Briefly justify your reply.

2. What would make the academia-driven actions for refugees economically sustainable in your opinion?

3. Please rate the following economic resources based on their importance to carry out academia-driven social actions. (scale 1-5, 1= not at all, 5=extremely)

Items:

1. Staff scarcity and availability
2. Funding
3. Entrepreneurial ability of staff
4. Digital tools
5. Location (to host event)

Section: Social sustainability

1. Do you believe that your institution has become more open to embrace social actions as part of its educational activities? Please justify.
2. What would make the academia-driven actions for refugees sustainable in terms of social impact in your opinion?
3. Please rate the following social skills based on their importance to carry out academia-driven social actions. (scale 1-5, 1= not at all, 5=extremely)

Items:

1. Active listening
2. Empathy
3. Communication
4. Emotional intelligence
5. Teamwork
6. Respect
7. Clear language
8. Community bonding

Annex II: Sustainability survey for HE students

The survey distributed to university students who participated in the AGILE WP3 and WP4 actions is presented below.

Survey title: Impact of the AGILE actions at individual level

Section: demographics

Name

Email

Affiliation

You live in: add country

You are:

- University student
- Academic staff
- Researcher
- Other

Section: Impact of the AGILE actions at individual level

1. Choose the AGILE actions you participated in.

- AGILE summer school (organised by UBM)
- Educational activities and workshops (organised by UBM)
- Educational activities and workshops (organised by UP8)
- Webinar: "Training for innovation and entrepreneurship skills of displaced and refugee academics" (organised by UL)
- CRASH COURSE 2: "Social & Digital Innovation for Development in Practice" (organised by W2L in collaboration with Anna Berti Suman)
- Digital lab (organised by W2L)
- DigiEduHack Hackathon (Challenge organised by W2L)
- Crowdsourcing sprint (organised by W2L)
- Actions organised by KTU library
- Focus groups and survey organised by LPNU
- Survey and online discussions organised by PRF

2. How much did your participation at the AGILE action/s increase your knowledge on refugee resilience and social actions? Rate the following items. (scale 1-5, 1= not at all, 5=extremely)

Items:

1. Academia's social responsibility
2. Academia-society cooperation
3. Private sector role in refugee resilience
4. Refugee entrepreneurship
5. Social innovation
6. Societal resilience

Section: Economic sustainability

3. What would make the academia-driven actions for refugees economically sustainable in your opinion?

4. Do you believe that participation in academia-driven social actions should be voluntary or remunerative? Briefly justify your answer.

5. On a scale from 1 (=not at all) to 5 (=extremely), how important do you think follow-up funding to turn participants' ideas into action is?

1= not at all

2= Slightly

3= Moderately

4= Very

5= Extremely

Section: Social sustainability

6. On a scale from 1 (=not at all) to 5 (=extremely), how likely is it that you will take part in academia-driven social actions in the future?

1= not at all

2= Slightly

3= Moderately

4= Very

5= Extremely

7. Do you feel more open to engage in actions that include multistakeholder collaboration for refugees' inclusion? Develop your thoughts here.

8. How much did your participation in the AGILE action/s increase your social skills for refugees' inclusion? Rate the following items. (scale 1-5, 1= not at all, 5=extremely)

Items:

1. Active listening
2. Empathy
3. Communication
4. Emotional intelligence
5. Teamwork
6. Respect
7. Clear language
8. Community bonding

AGILE

Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition.

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